

Supporting Information

for *Small*, DOI 10.1002/smll.202308857

Single-Step Functionalization Strategy of Graphene Microtransistor Array with Chemically Modified Aptamers for Biosensing Applications

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Figure S1. AFM images comparing bare graphene (a, d, g) to functionalized with NH_2 -TBA (b, c), Fm-TBA (e, f) and Ac-TBA (h, i) at $1\ \mu\text{M}$ concentration, at different sizes of scanning areas.

Figure S2. Raman spectrum of pristine graphene with the corresponding G and 2D at ~ 1582 and $\sim 2699\ \text{cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The intensity ratio between the two bands provides information about the number of layers of graphene, while the frequency position and ratio are related to the doping and the strain levels. The graphene structural defects are shown by an additional phonon contribution called the D band ($\sim 1348\ \text{cm}^{-1}$). This figure shows the comparison between the spectrum before and after Fm-TBA modification with a $2\ \mu\text{M}$ concentration.

Figure S3. a) Drain–source current (I_{ds}) versus gate–source voltage (V_{gs}), of one transistor functionalized with the bare graphene surface and after pyrene-COOH functionalization. The dashed lines represent the same curves with the CNP normalized at $V_{gs}=0$ V. b) CNP data extracted from transfer curves of an arrays of 48 transistors with the bare graphene surface and after the functionalization with pyrene-COOH. c) Drain–source current (I_{ds}) versus gate–source voltage (V_{gs}), of one transistor functionalized with the bare graphene surface and after pyrene-NH₂ functionalization. The dashed lines represent the same curves with the CNP normalized at $V_{gs}=0$ V. d) CNP data extracted from transfer curves of 48 transistors with the bare graphene surface and after the functionalization with pyrene-NH₂.

Figure S4. Scheme of the procedure for measurements and controls.

Figure S5. Variations in CNP from data obtained by the transfer curves performed in all the thrombin detection assays with gSGFETs functionalized with single-step strategy (Ac-TBA & Fm-TBA) and multi-step strategy (NH₂-TBA through pyrene-COOH), respectively. In the figures it is also included the control experiments with BSA –non-specific protein- and buffer PBS. Ctr1 (control 1) and Ctr2 (control 2) corresponds to the functionalized device before and after the detection of thrombin in PBS, respectively. Data plotted in graphs has been normalized by Control 1 ($\Delta\text{CNP} = \text{CNP}_{\text{Ctr1}} - \text{CNP}_{\text{Detection step}}$). Statistics are shown on top of each boxplot by comparison to pairs. In total, data shown comprises a total of 770 transistors, resulting in 5494 measurements, while four thrombin protein batches were employed to perform all the assays.

Figure S6. Linear calibration plot of ΔCNP (mV) versus logarithmic thrombin concentration (0.2, 2, 20 and 200 nM) with gSGFETs functionalized with Ac-TBA ($y = 11,75x + 15,12$), Fm-TBA ($y = 9,650x + 13,00$) and PyreneCOOH ($y = 8,758x + 10,57$).

Figure S7. Plots of the gSGFETs response, as changes in the CNP, with the three functionalization employed (Ac-TBA, Fm-TBA and NH₂-TBA via pyrene-COOH) with a) BSA at different concentrations employed as the selectivity control and b) after subsequent incubations of PBS employed as the blank.

Figure S8. QCM-D spectra using NH₂-scrambled aptamer as a control.

Control for sequence specificity: NH₂-scrambled sequence

Figure S9. Boxplots analysis for the different thrombin batches used with gSGFETs functionalized with Ac-TBA, Fm-TBA and NH₂-TBA via pyrene-COOH, respectively.

Figure S10. Table with the number of working transistors for each functionalization and batch (B1, B2, B3) for the n = 20 chips.

Transistors Number	AcTBA	FmTBA	Pyrene-COOH + NH ₂ -TBA
PBS	7	16	41
BSA	24	48	35
Control 1	114 (PBS=7; BSA=24; B1=22; B2=41; B3 =20)	169 (PBS=16; BSA=50; B1=40; B2=40; B3 =23)	205 (PBS=41; BSA=35 B1=40; B2=70; B3 =19)
Thrombin 0.2 nM	76 (B1=22; B2=37; B3=17)	92 (B1=36; B2=38; B3=18)	98 (B1=37; B2=45; B3=16)
Thrombin 2nM	78 (B1=20; B2 =40; B3 =18)	97 (B1=35; B2=40; B3 =22)	119 (B1=38; B2 =65; B3 =16)
Thrombin 20nM	79 (B1=22; B2 =40; B3 =17)	93 (B1=34; B2 =38; B3 =21)	117 (B1=35; B2 =67; B3 =15)
Thrombin 200nM	79 (B1=21; B2 =40; B3 =18)	94 (B1=32; B2 =40; B3 =22)	118 (B1=38; B2 =65; B3 =15)
Control 2	82 (B1=21; B2 =41; B3 =20)	97 (B1=34; B2 =40; B3 =23)	123 (B1=38; B2 =67; B3 =18)

Figure S11. Synthetic route for derivatization of thrombin aptamer with fluorenylmethyl and acridine moieties.

